

Patient Satisfaction and Total Hip Arthroplasty: A Review

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Abstract:

Introduction: Total Hip Arthroplasty (THA) is a critical procedure for alleviating pain and restoring mobility in patients with severe hip damage. Despite its effectiveness, variations in patient satisfaction highlight areas for improvement, particularly in pain management and functional recovery.

Methodology: This retrospective study analyzed data from 160 patients who underwent THA at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital between October 2020 and August 2023. Patient satisfaction was measured through standardized questionnaires, with regression analysis employed to identify predictors of satisfaction.

Results: The findings revealed high satisfaction with functional mobility (mean score: 8.2) but lower satisfaction with pain management (mean score: 7.8). Age was a significant predictor, with younger patients generally more satisfied.

Conclusion: The study underscores the necessity of enhanced pain management strategies and targeted patient education to manage expectations more effectively, particularly for older adults undergoing THA.

Recommendation: Tailored preoperative counseling and personalized pain management plans are advised to improve satisfaction and outcomes in THA patients, focusing on age-specific needs and expectations.

Keywords: Total Hip Arthroplasty, Patient Satisfaction, Pain Management, Functional Mobility, Age Predictors.

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Introduction

Total Hip Arthroplasty (THA) remains one of the most transformative and successful orthopedic interventions for patients suffering from debilitating hip joint diseases such as osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and traumatic arthritis [1,2]. This procedure not only alleviates pain but also restores mobility and substantially improves the quality of life. However, despite the generally favorable outcomes associated with THA, patient satisfaction can vary widely, influenced by a myriad of factors including pain management, functional recovery, and individual patient expectations [3,4].

Recent advancements in surgical techniques, prosthetic design, and perioperative care have undoubtedly enhanced the outcomes of THA. Nonetheless, there is a growing recognition within the medical community that understanding patient perspectives—specifically, their satisfaction with the procedure—is crucial for optimizing postoperative care and improving overall treatment efficacy [5]. Patient satisfaction is multifaceted, encompassing various dimensions such as pain

levels, functional mobility, personal care ability, and overall quality of life post-surgery [6].

The interplay between clinical outcomes and patient-reported satisfaction is complex, influenced by preoperative conditions, surgical technique, postoperative rehabilitation, and psychosocial factors. Given these complexities, it becomes imperative to rigorously examine the determinants of satisfaction to identify areas where improvements can be made to enhance patient experiences and outcomes [7,8,9].

This study aims to evaluate the factors influencing patient satisfaction following Total Hip Arthroplasty at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, assessing the impact of demographic characteristics, clinical outcomes, and patient expectations on their overall satisfaction with the procedure. Through this analysis, the study seeks to provide actionable insights that can help tailor treatment approaches to better meet patient needs and expectations, ultimately enhancing patient satisfaction with THA.

Methodology

Study Design

This study employed a retrospective review design to evaluate patient satisfaction following total hip arthroplasty (THA). The goal was to assess various factors influencing patient outcomes and satisfaction over a defined period using historical data.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar. Data were collected from October 2020 to August 2023, covering a range of THA cases performed at the institution during this time.

Participants: The study included a total of 160 patients who underwent THA at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. These patients were reviewed based on their medical records, focusing on those who had completed a minimum of six months post-operatively to ensure a thorough assessment of long-term outcomes.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients who underwent total hip arthroplasty at the hospital.
- Patients who completed at least six months of follow-up to provide a comprehensive evaluation of both immediate and longer-term outcomes.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who did not complete the six-month follow-up period.
- Cases with incomplete or insufficient data for analysis.

Bias: To address potential sources of bias, the study ensured that only patients who had completed the minimum follow-up period were included, reducing the likelihood of skewed short-term outcome data. Data were extracted from standardized medical records to minimize selection

bias and ensure consistency in the information collected.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected retrospectively from the hospital's medical records, focusing on patients who had completed at least six months post-surgery. The data collected included demographic information, clinical history, details of the surgical procedure, post-operative care, and follow-up outcomes. Patient satisfaction was assessed using standardized questionnaires administered during follow-up visits, which covered pain levels, functional mobility, personal care ability, and overall quality of life.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patient sample. Regression analysis was employed to examine the relationships between patient satisfaction and various predictors such as age, gender, pre-existing comorbidities, and the complexity of the surgery. Statistical significance was determined using a p-value of less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects. Patient data were anonymized to protect confidentiality, and the study protocol was reviewed and approved by the relevant institutional review board or ethics committee at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. All procedures were conducted with a focus on maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of patient information.

Result

The study evaluated patient satisfaction following total hip arthroplasty (THA) for 160 patients at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. The results are presented in detailed tables and graphs to illustrate the demographic characteristics, satisfaction scores, and relationships between patient satisfaction and various predictors.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (n=160)	Percentage (%)
Age		
50-59 years	45	28.1
60-69 years	70	43.8
70-79 years	40	25.0
80+ years	5	3.1
Gender		
Male	75	46.9
Female	85	53.1
Pre-existing Comorbidities		
Diabetes	40	25.0
Hypertension	50	31.3
Both	20	12.5
None	50	31.3

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, and pre-existing comorbidities. The majority of participants were between 60 and 69 years old (43.8%), with a slight female predominance (53.1%). Comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes were prevalent in 56.3% of the cohort.

Table 2: Patient Satisfaction Scores

Satisfaction Domain	Mean Score (±SD)	Range
Pain Levels	7.8 (±1.5)	4 - 10
Functional Mobility	8.2 (±1.4)	5 - 10
Personal Care Ability	8.0 (±1.6)	4 - 10
Overall Quality of Life	8.1 (±1.5)	5 - 10

Table 2 presents the mean satisfaction scores for various domains assessed using standardized questionnaires. Scores range from 4 to 10, with higher scores indicating better satisfaction. The highest satisfaction was reported for functional mobility (mean score 8.2), while pain levels had the lowest mean score (7.8).

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Predictors of Patient Satisfaction

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	p-value
Age	-0.05	0.02	0.015
Gender (Female)	0.20	0.15	0.180
Diabetes	-0.25	0.18	0.175
Hypertension	-0.10	0.17	0.540
Complexity of Surgery	-0.30	0.20	0.120

Table 3 shows the results of the regression analysis examining predictors of patient satisfaction. Age is a significant predictor of satisfaction with a negative coefficient, indicating that older patients reported slightly lower satisfaction scores. Other factors, including gender, pre-existing comorbidities, and complexity of the surgery, did not show significant associations with patient satisfaction at the 0.05 significance level.

Figure 1: Distribution of Satisfaction Scores Across Domains

This bar graph shows the mean satisfaction scores for various domains such as Pain Levels, Functional Mobility, Personal Care Ability, and Overall Quality of Life. Functional mobility scored the highest, indicating that patients were most satisfied in this area, while pain levels received the lowest mean score.

Figure 2: Relationship Between Age and Satisfaction Scores

The scatter plot illustrates how satisfaction scores vary with age across the patient cohort. A trend line suggests that younger age groups generally reported higher satisfaction, particularly noticeable in domains such as pain levels and functional mobility. This visualization helps in understanding the impact of age on patient satisfaction following total hip arthroplasty

Discussion

The retrospective review of 160 patients undergoing total hip arthroplasty (THA) at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital revealed significant findings in patient satisfaction across various domains [10,11]. The data indicated the highest satisfaction in functional mobility (mean score: 8.2) and the lowest in pain levels (mean score: 7.8). Age emerged as a significant predictor of satisfaction, with younger patients reporting higher satisfaction scores, particularly in pain management and mobility [12,13].

The elevated satisfaction scores in functional mobility suggest that THA effectively restores physical function, aligning with the primary goals of the procedure—reducing disability and enhancing quality of life [14]. Conversely, the lower scores in pain levels may indicate ongoing challenges in post-operative pain management or potentially unrealistic expectations regarding pain relief post-surgery [15]. The influence of age on satisfaction highlights the potential impact of physiological resilience and recovery capabilities, which tend to diminish with advancing age.

The findings corroborate existing studies that have identified functional outcomes as a critical determinant of patient satisfaction following orthopedic surgeries, including THA (Smith et al.,

2019). However, the relatively lower satisfaction scores for pain management contrast with studies like Jones et al. (2021), which reported higher satisfaction with pain outcomes. This discrepancy could be attributed to variations in pain management protocols, patient demographics, or surgical techniques across different healthcare settings [1,2,16].

The variations in satisfaction with pain management might be explained by differences in patient expectations, which are often shaped by preoperative counseling and the patients' health literacy [17]. Furthermore, the correlation between age and satisfaction can be elucidated by the physiological changes associated with aging, such as reduced muscle mass and slower healing, which may affect the perception of recovery and satisfaction. The data suggests a need for tailored preoperative education that manages expectations more effectively, especially concerning pain and recovery in older adults [11,18].

These findings underscore the importance of a comprehensive approach to patient education and preoperative counseling, particularly in managing expectations about pain and functional recovery post-THA. Healthcare providers may need to consider age-specific strategies in both surgical planning and post-operative care to enhance satisfaction across all age groups. Furthermore, ongoing efforts to improve pain management protocols could be crucial in raising patient satisfaction levels, potentially involving more personalized pain management strategies based on individual patient profiles and pre-existing conditions [19,20].

Conclusion

The study's results contribute valuable insights into the factors influencing patient satisfaction following THA, with significant implications for clinical practice. By addressing the identified gaps in pain management and adjusting care approaches based on patient age, healthcare providers can potentially enhance overall patient satisfaction and outcomes following hip replacement surgeries.

References

- Smith J, Chen X, Zhang X. Outcomes of total hip arthroplasty: a systematic review. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2020;15(1):21.
- Johnson LR, Harris B. The impact of preoperative patient education on the outcomes of hip replacement surgery. *Orthop Nurs.* 2021;40 (2) :95-102.
- Wang F, Scott IA, Tran P. Patient satisfaction: understanding the factors that influence post-operative outcomes in orthopaedic surgery. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2019;101(15):1345-1351.
- Lee YK, Chung CY, Koo KH, Lee KM, Ji HM, Park MS. Factors affecting patient satisfaction following total joint arthroplasty. *J Arthroplasty.* 2022;37(1):122-129.
- Brown TE, Larson B, Shen F, Moskal JT. Pain management and satisfaction in post-THA patients: a multidisciplinary approach. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2020;478(6):1373-1381.
- Morrison R, Macnair R. Quality of life after total hip replacement: a review of the literature. *J Orthop Res.* 2021;39(1):10-18.
- Patel H, Booth RE Jr. Improvement of patient satisfaction in total hip arthroplasty: a psychological perspective. *J Psychol.* 2023;157(2) :198-209.
- Kim D, Park WH, Lee SH. Age as a predictor of satisfaction outcomes in total hip arthroplasty. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg.* 2021;141(8): 1193-1201.
- Thomas S, Palmer J, Phillips B, Harris K. Managing expectations: the role of information provision in patient satisfaction after orthopedic surgery. *Patient Educ Couns.* 2020;103(5) :995-1002.
- Norris T, Anderson R. Gender differences in postoperative outcomes and satisfaction in hip arthroplasty patients. *J Clin Orthop Trauma.* 2022;13(3):240-246.
- Evans JT, Walker RW, Evans JP, Blom AW, Sayers A, Whitehouse MR. How comorbidities influence patient satisfaction: a cohort study of THA recipients. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* 2019; 27(8):1145-1152.
- Gupta S, Hawker GA, Laporte A, Croxford R, Coyte PC. The economic aspects of hip replacement: hospital costs and reimbursement issues from a longitudinal study. *J Health Econ.* 2021; 70:102316.
- Marshall DA, Pykerman K, Werle J, Lorenzetti DL, Wasylak T, Noseworthy T, et al. Health system factors affecting patient satisfaction in THA: a systematic review. *J Eval Clin Pract.* 2021;27(2):473-485.
- Zhang Y, Delzell E, Xie F, Baddley JW, Spettell C, McMurray JJ, et al. Impact of timing of physical therapy initiation on outcomes of total hip arthroplasty. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg.* 2020;28(4):e162-e168.
- Hardy S, Goubar A. Risk factors and predictive models for post-operative pain following hip arthroplasty. *J Pain Res.* 2019; 12:2097-2110.
- Foster S, Lee C. Cultural influences on patient satisfaction: insights from an ethnographic study of Asian and Western patients. *J Transcult Nurs.* 2022;33(1):75-82.
- Monroe K, Murphy S, Dewar C, O'Sullivan T. Patient education techniques for improving satisfaction and outcomes in hip arthroplasty: a comparative study. *Patient Prefer Adherence.* 2023; 17:457-468.
- O'Brien S, Weaver F, Padilla M, Lurie JD, Kurtz S, Bozic KJ. Long-term patient-reported outcomes following total hip arthroplasty: a cohort study. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2022;480(1):112-119.
- Norris N, Hopkins D. Technique and technology in hip arthroplasty: how surgical innovations impact patient satisfaction. *J Orthop Sci.* 2021;26(1):18-24.
- Patel V, Lee K, Mears SC. The role of infection control practices in influencing patient satisfaction rates following hip arthroplasty. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 2020;41(9): 1045-1051.